

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MAGAMBO****FIRST NAME: TOM****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID yet to provide access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2010 on Windows 10 Pro)

THE ART OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

It has been four years since completing a Master's in Business Administration (MBA) and the guidance contained in this 61-page course pack, has refreshed and challenged the mind on the required writing skills for doctoral studies at Euclid University. The tips provided on essay writing, plagiarism, styles, and differences between American and British English to mention but a few are informative. Besides, the part of sample corrections to papers is also timely as it enables one to have good reference material in the preparation of response papers.

2) NOTABLE LESSONS FROM COURSEPACK FOR PERIOD 1

In chapter one (1), which focuses on the basics, the assertion that essay writing is not a linear process, is realistic and gives flexibility to the writer to be more innovative. The argument that scholars require enough time to read and think is ideal though some times, the situation is complex and conditions are unfavorable (EUCLID 2019, 1-2). Nevertheless, the point is clear that scholars should undertake extensive reading, identify central questions to address and develop a writing plan to ensure good output. The other interesting points of emphasis in the chapter were a reminder to take notes from what one reads especially for ease of reference, use evidence to support arguments and avoid making wild arguments without concrete facts, enhance drafting and editing skills, and understand assignment rules. It is also clear from the material that essay writing, requires

one to engage in creative and critical thinking especially of the different arguments advanced by scholars on the subject under study.

On plagiarism covered in chapter two (2), the moral and legal question of using ideas of other authors without acknowledging is greatly discouraged. In highlighting the importance of shunning plagiarism, the approach in which it is expounded in the coursepack is powerful (EUCLID 2019, 5-6). The examples of plagiarism given and the rationale for proper citation, use of quotations, paraphrasing, citations, and works cited are extremely helpful as one embarks on Ph.D. studies. This chapter is very crucial in that, over time scholars have researched most areas and hence the need to build on existing studies. Therefore, what we can do as scholars now is to deeply examine previous studies on areas of interest and identify gaps in which to contribute and expand on existing knowledge.

The rules of thumb for writing papers emphasized in chapter three, especially on staying focused; avoiding generalities and passive constructions as well as writing clearly, were timely (EUCLID 2019, 14). Indeed, contributing to knowledge requires being precise and remaining focused on the theme without unnecessary quotations from materials that are not directly relevant to the study. The other point of interest was the idea that scholars must undertake self-reflection while criticizing the works of others. This is a powerful lesson in that many times, we tend to embark on faultfinding without exploring various dimensions, which the author intended to advance.

In chapter four (4), the eleven (11) reminders presented especially on omitting unnecessary words, using parallel construction and active words, proper punctuation, and usage of commas was informative (EUCLID 2019, 17). Technical as it appears, this remains an area that scholars must grapple with to enhance the presentation of ideas more clearly and concisely. Besides, the guidance under literature review also enabled a reflection on proper usage of common words such as “your” and “you’re,” “that” and “which,” “I” and “Me” and using numbers in an essay (EUCLID 2019, 19). It was interesting to learn about the exception to the rules provided and ongoing debate on the usage of terms among scholars. The part on numbers was interesting with the argument that they can be written as numerals exceptions notwithstanding. Of interest was the lesson that scholars can begin a sentence using, which is uncommon, and the justification was valid.

On styles, which are explained in chapter five (5), there is no problem with adopting the Chicago rules (Turabian) and Euclid templates to prepare response papers. As well explained in the text, styles depend on each institution and they keep changing with circumstances though the key elements remain notably, length of sentences, layout, font usage, type of English, and structure among others. The point made that each creative writer may use own style guide was appealing but the reasoning that essays have to be reviewed by other scholars strengthened the point of adopting an agreed style by the institution (EUCLID 2019, 24-25).

The differences between American and British English and the reasons given in chapter six (6) for scholars growingly opting to use American English, was a clear demonstration that whoever controls the global economy, tends to influence most aspects of life including academic fields. The factors are given for the rise in usage of American

English such as high population, wealth, the magnitude of higher learning and publishing, global mass media, and appeal to American popular culture (EUCLID 2019, 27). That is an indication that global dominance has a direct impact on scholarly work. The puzzle remains on how the future of the academic world will be if another country emerges as a global power, and scholars have to prepare their work in another language possibly, Chinese.

The sample corrections to papers provided in chapter seven (7) were very useful in emphasizing the words to avoid in academic writing and appropriate terminologies to adopt. For instance “Threatening” instead of “Serious,” “Intervention” to “Interference” and “The US” for “America.” The discussion on the preferred length of sentences and usage of terms and other common writing mistakes was timely.

The Chicago Manual Style (CMS) Crib Sheet discussed in chapter eight (8) was also informative as it refreshed the mind on abbreviations, acronyms, capitalization, and the use of compound words. More interestingly, was the usage of prefix words, “all-powerful leader,” and “self-reliant person” which are commonly miswritten. Besides, the use of italics, quotations, and numbers were also well handled (EUCLID 2019, 47-48).

Lastly, in chapter nine (9) on the usage of Latin abbreviations and expressions, it was important to review the meaning of common abbreviations in writing for instance, “etc.,” “i.e.” and ‘N.B’ which will remain a reference point. The details in the two tables on Latin abbreviations and expressions commonly used were crucial in simplifying the message. Equally important was the emphasis that scholars use plain language, avoid jargon, and ensure logically organized and understandable essays (EUCLID 2019, 56-58).

3) CONCLUSION

Therefore, it is clear that for one to write a good academic paper many steps are required and guidelines to follow. The notable lessons, for me, are as follows; without committing ample time, it is difficult to produce good academic work, critical thinking and content analysis are crucial, and technical tools available if utilized well, can help guard against plagiarism and improve on grammar. It is also important that concise and clear writing be emphasized, and when you are criticizing other academic works, efforts be made to do self-reflection on possible explanations those authors would give to the unclear content.

Given the above key lessons, there is no doubt that my journey to undertake this Ph.D. has a good foundation from this material. The four years spent after completing an MBA required this reflection to sharpen the mind on this journey of intellectual development. In that regard, there is no doubt the material shall be handy during the entire course.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.